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Case Study

Insights Into Candle Syndrome: A Rare Autoinflammatory Disorder

Ahalya U.¹, Praveena Prasad¹, Shaiju Dharan², Dhanya Dharman^{*3}

¹Pharm D Intern (Department of Pharmacy Practice, Ezhuthachan College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Marayamuttom, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India)

²Principal/HOD (Department of Pharmacy Practice, Ezhuthachan College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Marayamuttom, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India)

³Associate Professor, (Department of Pharmacy Practice, Ezhuthachan College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Marayamuttom, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India)

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ABSTRACT

CANDLE syndrome is an abbreviated form of Chronic Atypical Neutrophilic Dermatitis with Lipodystrophy and Elevated temperature which has been recently identified, is an auto inflammatory syndrome that typically starts at an early age and is characterized by recurring fever, skin lesions and inflammations affecting multiple systems in the body. [1] There are only 60 known CANDLE syndrome cases in the world. We report a 7-year-old female paediatric patient with CANDLE syndrome.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic Atypical Neutrophilic Dermatitis with Lipodystrophy and Elevated temperature, is a rare genetic auto inflammatory disease caused by abnormalities in the way the multicatalytic system proteasome-immunoproteasome functions. CANDLE syndrome typically begins in the first few months of life, with the most common initial sign being daily or near-daily fever or slightly elevated temperature below 38.3° C. Despite these

temperature changes, the overall health and well-being of individuals with CANDLE syndrome are generally minimally affected or even normal. Exposure to cold temperatures can sometimes trigger temperature elevation and skin lesions. In CANDLE syndrome, the dysfunction of the proteasome-immunoproteasome system leads to a constant state of inflammation, with occasional flare-ups. This dysfunction causes an excessive release of type 1 interferons, which leads to the

***Corresponding Author:** Dhanya Dharman

Address: Department of Pharmacy Practice, Ezhuthachan College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Marayamuttom, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India).

Email ✉: dhanyadharman07@gmail.com

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build-up of waste proteins within cells. This accumulation of waste proteins causes cellular stress, triggering even more type 1 interferon production, creating a cycle of inflammation. Every day triggers like cold, stress or infections can stimulate the secretion of type 1 interferons, resulting in severe inflammatory episodes that can affect any organ in the body. Skin lesions are the first visible signs of CANDLE syndrome and tend to persist throughout the course of the disease, although they may become less noticeable after puberty. Lipodystrophy characterized by abnormal fat distribution, usually starts in early childhood and is well established before puberty. In the long term, joint manifestations that can cause disability. Throughout a patient's life, they may experience different acute episodes of the disease, either spontaneously or triggered by common factors, affecting various organs in the body.^[1]

Laboratory investigations include ESR, CRP and CBC. Liver enzyme levels are usually slightly elevated, which may be due to lipodystrophy itself. Additionally, metabolic disturbances caused by lipodystrophy can lead to higher triglyceride levels. In some cases, there may be elevated levels of muscle enzymes like CPK and aldolase, indicating ongoing muscle involvement. Tests for autoimmune markers and auto antibodies typically show negative result, although some patients may have increased levels of anti-nuclear antibodies. Immunoglobulin levels in the blood are usually normal. Bone marrow and lymph node biopsies often show no significant abnormalities, only reactive changes.^[2] Genetic testing is currently the only way to confirm a CANDLE syndrome. It occurs when the PSMB8 gene is not working properly. Other genes linked to this condition include PSMB4, PSMA3 and POMP. Typically, CANDLE syndrome is inherited in autosomal recessive pattern. However, in cases where there are variants in the POMP gene, it may be inherited in an autosomal dominant pattern. An advanced

skin biopsy may also help with a diagnosis. Other laboratory and imaging abnormalities are seen during acute inflammatory attacks; these are dependent on the organs affected by inflammation.^[3]

There is currently no single treatment consistently effective for CANDLE syndrome. While oral corticosteroids and methotrexate may offer some relief, methotrexate is typically considered the initial treatment option. NSAIDs might help partially manage fever, but medications like dapsone or colchicine proven ineffective. Other options like cyclosporine, azathioprine or intravenous immunoglobulins have shown minimal improvement. Even anti-TNF drugs like etanercept have not been beneficial and can exacerbate the condition. In acute episodes, systemic corticosteroids along with organ-specific therapy may be necessary. A compassionate use treatment protocol has been initiated for CANDLE syndrome involving the use of selective JAK 1/2 kinase inhibitor baricitinib. Patients who did not respond adequately to conventional therapies or needed high doses of corticosteroids where administered oral baricitinib. Ultimately, it's essential to offer physical therapy to prevent joint contractures and provide tailored organ-specific therapy to manage CANDLE syndrome effectively.^[4]

CANDLE patients experience diverse outcomes, ranging from potentially fatal acute inflammation attacks in vital organs to prolonged survival with varying levels of disability.

CASE REPORT

A 7 years old female paediatric patient was presented with complaints of fever for 25 days, rhinitis, cough and nausea for 1 day.

On the day of admission temperature was elevated (101° F). Laboratory investigation revealed a depletion in haemoglobin (10.4 g/dL) and an elevation ESR (55 mm/hr) and CRP (39.6 mg/L) levels. CANDLE syndrome was diagnosed by

next-generation sequencing (NGS) which shows an impression of heterozygous autosomal dominant nonsense variation in exon 5 of SAMDL 9 gene possible CANDLE syndrome, flow cytometry suggestive of ALPS 3.5%, TCR ab DNT among CD3 cells 5.6%, pancytopenia with normocellular marrow and trilineage maturation. The patient was treated with Neb Levosalbutamol 1.25 mg Q4H, Neb Budesonide 0.5 mg Q6H, Syp. Clarithromycin 6 ml BD, T. Lansoprazole 15mg OD, Syp. Chlorpheniramine + phenylephrine 4 ml TID, Inj. Ceftriaxone 850 mg BD, T. Baricitinib 2 mg OD, Syp. Paracetamol 5 ml stat and T. Folic acid 5 mg ½-0-0. After 3 days of treatment, patient symptoms were improved and discharged with the advice of Neb Levosalbutamol 1.2mg Q4H, Neb Budesonide 0.5mg Q6H, Syp. Clarithromycin 6ml BD, Inj. Ceftriaxone 850mg BD, T. Lanzoprazole 15mg OD, Syp. Chlorpheniramine + phenylephrine 4ml TDS.

DISCUSSION

CANDLE syndrome, an acronym for chronic atypical neutrophilic dermatosis with lipodystrophy and elevated temperature, represents an autoinflammatory condition linked to proteasome dysfunction, resulting in aberrant type 1 interferon signalling. It typically manifests within the first year of a child's life, presenting with symptoms such as hepatomegaly, elevated liver enzymes, chronic anaemia and stunted growth in height and weight. [5] While CANDLE syndrome typically emerges in infancy across nearly all cases, the presentation of signs and symptoms can vary widely among affected children. Nevertheless, many of these symptoms can lead to significant pain and discomfort, including joint pain, developmental delays, recurrent fevers, purpura, swollen eyelids, gradual fat loss in multiple body regions, muscle contractures, stiffness and seizures. When a child exhibits characteristic skin lesions, fat loss and early onset fevers physicians may consider

CANDLE syndrome as a potential diagnosis. Confirmation of CANDLE syndrome currently relies on genetic testing as the primary diagnostic method, while advanced skin biopsy techniques may also aid in the diagnostic process. While glucocorticoids effectively manage acute inflammation, their prolonged usage is hindered by significant side effects. JAK inhibitors offer a promising solution for sustained disease symptom control in children with CANDLE syndrome, presenting fewer severe side effects and potentially enhancing their quality of life in long term.

CONCLUSION

Chronic Atypical Neutrophilic Dermatitis with Lipodystrophy and Elevated Temperature (CANDLE) syndrome is a rare autoinflammatory disorder characterized by recurrent episodes of fever, skin lesions and systemic inflammation. Typically, these skin lesions present as annular erythematous plaques with overlying violaceous borders and can involve various body sites. Additionally, affected individuals often experience joint contractures, lipodystrophy and growth retardation. The syndrome typically manifests early in infancy or childhood with symptoms persisting into adulthood.

Diagnosis is based on clinical features including skin biopsy findings and genetic testing for mutations in gene. Management involves a multidisciplinary approach aimed at controlling inflammation and improving quality of life, often utilizing immunosuppressive medications and supportive therapies. Due to its rarity and complex presentation, further research is needed to better understand the pathophysiology of CANDLE syndrome and develop more effective treatment strategies.

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